

**THE ROLE OF ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE
IMPLEMENTATION OF EFFECTIVE MECHANISMS TO STIMULATE
TRADE ACTIVITIES OF EXPORTING ENTERPRISES IN TERMS OF
EXPORT-ORIENTED ECONOMIC POLICY.**

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Abstract: As a result of technological progress and economic globalization, manufacturers are encouraged to meet domestic demand easily and to start supplying products to foreign markets. Producers are trying to gain a foothold by fully complying with the import requirements and procedures of the new market. This process requires legal, organizational and financial support from the government due to the complexity of import requirements and processes in the mobile markets. Therefore, in international practice, many companies have implemented and effectively use systems of organizational and financial support of exporting enterprises.

Key words: exporting enterprises, financial support, subsidy, compensation.

The effective organization of export policy is one of the most important and urgent issues facing the governments not only of Uzbekistan, but also all countries of the world. Therefore, in recent years, liberalization and simplification of export activities, diversification of the structure and geography of exports, expansion and mobilization of the export potential of industries and regions of the economy, expansion of the volume and range of exports to the European Union within the "GSP+" program and membership in the World Trade Organization have done significant work.

In addition, a system of additional support to export activities of business entities was created within the national system of support to exports. In order to ensure the continuity of export activities of local enterprises in this system the "Made in Uzbekistan" program is being implemented to allocate the necessary

credit funds to finance exports, promotion of Uzbek brands and products abroad by participating in international exhibitions and presentations. the introduction of international standards and certificates for exporting companies, reimbursement of advertising and travel expenses abroad has begun.

After all, in today's increasingly fierce competition in the world markets it is essential to radically improve the competitiveness of our economy, to strengthen support for enterprises that produce for export, encourage the participation of farmers, small businesses and private enterprises in export activities.

As a result of work carried out in our country to support exports and create favorable conditions for exporting enterprises in 2022, the country exported goods and services worth more than 19.3 billion dollars, resulting in an increase in the export potential of the republic by almost 60% compared to 2016.

In the last 6 years, the main driver of export growth has been textiles (exports of \$3.2 billion, up 3.5 times), electrical appliances (\$259 million, up 5 times), supported by exports of high value-added products from local industrial enterprises, such as construction materials (\$611 million, up 4 times), chemical industry products (\$371 million, up 3 times).

Last year alone, 2,400 new companies were involved in export activities, which exported \$1.1 billion worth of products. The geography of exports expanded with the markets of 52 new countries, silk dresses for women to Italy and Latvia, copper wire products to Cameroon, sewing machines to Turkey and Iran, washing machines to Moldova, national musical instruments to Israel, mosh flour to Korea, electronic data storage to France, for the first time instruments and auto parts were supplied to Angola.

However, there are prospects for increasing the potential of Uzbekistan's export sector. In particular, the fact that the number of exporting enterprises is relatively small compared to the total number of industrial enterprises, or that the scale of use of opportunities and benefits provided to exporting enterprises remains at a low level can serve as clear evidence of our view.

To this end, it is particularly important to study the global experience and apply the best of these experiences to Uzbekistan. From this point of view, the study deeply analyzes the experience of developed countries of the world in terms of export support.

In particular, the Hungarian Export Promotion Agency (HEPA) is engaged in providing greater organizational and advisory support to exporters. Financial support is mainly provided by organizing free international exhibitions, business missions and trainings. There are no direct types of financial assistance to the exporter.

Types of financial assistance provided by the Russian Export Center (REC) are realized through specialized institutions. In particular, pre-export financing and guarantees are provided by JSC "Roseximbank", and insurance services are provided by JSC "EXIAR". Participation in international exhibitions and business missions, reimbursement of costs of certification, patenting and scientific research, as well as consulting and information services are also provided.

In addition, the center provides financial assistance in the form of coverage of up to 80% of the cost of transporting industrial products and up to 3% of the interest rate on export loans.

QazTrade" Trade Policy Development Center under the Ministry of Trade and Integration of the Republic of Kazakhstan participates in trade fairs, business events, trainings, contests and tenders, promotions, trade missions, branches, trading floors and warehouses abroad. provides financial support for the costs of renting, certification, accreditation and standardization, registration of trademarks, registration on e-commerce sites. The center also partially covers the costs of transporting innovative products.

To support local exporters in the UK, the government provides incentives, information, access to overseas markets and financial assistance.

To support exporting businesses in the country, a special platform, Great.gov.uk, was developed in 2016 for businesses that need guidance on how to export. Enterprises planning to enter foreign markets will be assisted in

developing an export plan and solving possible problems, as well as in the broad promotion of products in foreign markets.

In Germany, the most important element of state support for exports is the provision of financial measures, in particular credit, insurance, and state guarantees. Meanwhile, other financial measures to stimulate exports include:

- exemption of exporters from payment of value added tax;
- subsidizing certain industries (e.g. shipbuilding, aerospace and coal mining);
- financial support for export-oriented research and development.

Euler Hermes Insurance Company plays a key role in the system of financial support of exports by the state. The company provides insurance protection of foreign trade operations of German exporters. Under its terms, direct financing of German exports is carried out by specialized state credit organizations and private banks.

Also, the main public institutions in financing of German exports are the KfW Development Bank and the export credit society "AKA". These institutions provide commercial credits at preferential rates within the framework of state financial support to national exports.

The export credit company "AKA", in turn, provides loans, refinancing services, risk sharing, and export operations.

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